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The Impact of Media Strategy on Local Radio Stations: A Case Study on Drug Addiction Through Reports From DJA-FM Radio, During the Period 2016-2020

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the topic of media strategy in local radio stations, taking the issue of drug abuse as addressed in the reports of DJA-FM, Radio as a case study. The subject is presented and structured into chapters and sections according to the planned outline, as follows:

The first chapter of this study discusses the role of local radio stations and their broadcasting of programs on the dangers and harmful effects of drugs in society. It includes three sections that cover the stages of radio broadcasting, the types of radio stations, their capacities, characteristics, importance, and the tools of communication.

The first section focuses on radio programs, the skills required to prepare such programs, radio influence, and the target audience.

The second section addresses drugs, their types, and the harms resulting from drug abuse.

The third and final section sheds light on DJA-FM, Radio, revealing its nature, its development, and the types of programs it offers to the community.

Through this study, the researcher reached several findings, including:

Local radio stations serve as an effective tool for awareness campaigns and for reinforcing educational messages within society.

DJA-FM, Radio has improved its performance in order to enhance its awareness programs aimed at large segments of the population.

Upon completing the final form of this study, the researcher recommends the following:

Despite the efforts made by local radio stations to raise awareness among the Chadian population about the dangers of drugs, there remains a need to intensify these efforts to reach a wider societal segment.

Local radio stations should improve certain aspects of their work environment, particularly internal facilities, and provide written documents and archives that researchers and intellectuals can consult.

KEYWORDS: Strategy, Media, Local Radio Stations, Drugs.

INTRODUCTION

Audio media, such as radio, are a medium that impacts the public through its awareness programs. Local radio stations constantly work to educate and raise awareness within society. As a tool that addresses all segments of society, they influence people in one way or another. Most of the programs offered by local radio stations are beneficial to society and aim to reduce some of the problems encountered, particularly the phenomenon of drug use. This scourge affects most societies worldwide, burdening governments with legal proceedings and efforts to combat it. However, despite all these governmental efforts, it continues to spread within communities, and young people are the most affected group, trapped by drugs. The efforts of governments, as well as local media, whether audio or visual, continue to aim to combat this dangerous phenomenon and reduce it through the implementation of strategic plans. These plans support joint programs led by governments in coordination with other local media (radio, television and newspapers), with the aim of combating this phenomenon.

We also note that the majority of local radio stations have offered targeted programs addressing this phenomenon, despite the current challenges that necessitate a mastery of the scientific foundations for designing and preparing awareness programs aimed at resolving such diverse social phenomena. Audible radio has become a leading means of communication used to raise awareness in society in terms of its impact. Despite radio's growing role in the communication process and its unlimited potential for education, training, culture, guidance, and orientation, its effective use suffers greatly from the lack of appropriate scientific planning¹. Recent years have brought progress and well-being to humankind through

¹ Mostafa Mohamed Issa Fallatah : Auditory broadcasting as a means of communication and education, King Faisal University, 1st edition, 1998.

scientific and technological advancements and the industrial revolution, making travel from one country to another easier. This has contributed to the mixing of customs, traditions, and values, some beneficial and others detrimental. Among these harmful habits, their effects are not limited to destroying the life of the dependent individual, but their impacts also extend to the family, to society as a whole, and to humanity ².

The importance of research:

The importance of this research is as follows:

1. This study addresses an important social issue, namely the phenomenon of drug use. 2. It aims to find a solution to combat this phenomenon among young people. 3. It seeks to intensify awareness campaigns and programs broadcast by local radio stations. 4. It aims to end drug use in society. 5. It seeks to identify the parties involved in the introduction of drugs into society.

Research objectives

The research objectives include the following:

1- To understand the local radio stations in N'Djamena, the capital city, and their perceived role in society. 2- To highlight the useful awareness programs offered by these radio stations. 3- To closely examine whether the awareness messages broadcast by local radio stations are well received by the target audience. 4- To identify the challenges hindering the effectiveness of local radio stations in broadcasting their educational and awareness messages. 5- To verify whether local radio stations have actually offered programs that contribute to reducing the problem of drug use in society.

Research problem

This research addresses a real problem in society: drug use among young people. The researcher seeks to understand the effectiveness of local radio stations in combating this phenomenon, given that a large number of young people use drugs without oversight from the relevant authorities. This problem led the researcher to ask the following question: what role do local radio stations play in the fight against drugs, and what influence do they have on users?

Local radio stations are thus considered a media tool that helps society address drug use by intensifying awareness programs, which should be specifically targeted at young people and adolescents, as they are the most vulnerable group to this serious scourge.

Research questions

The research questions include the following points:

1- What is the role of DJA-FM radio in raising awareness and educating the public about the dangers of drugs?
2- What is the influence of DJA-FM radio's programs on its listeners?
3- What type of awareness programs does DJA-FM radio offer?
4- Are there specific programs to combat drug use? 5- Have these programs contributed to solving the problem of drug use? 6- Does DJA-FM radio offer specific programs to combat drug use?

Research Hypotheses

1. Local radio stations contributed to providing awareness and cultural programs regarding drug use. 2. The programs offered by local radio stations influenced the reduction of drug use among young people. 3. Everything offered by local radio stations was well received by the target audience. 4. Some local radio stations fulfilled their role regarding drug use. 5. Some young people were exposed to the awareness programs offered by local radio stations to educate society about drugs.

Research methodology

The researcher uses the descriptive and analytical method, considered the most appropriate for this study, to describe the most important details of local radio stations and their modes of operation.

Research population

The research population is that of the city of N'Djamena and the researcher will take a sample from this population.

Limitations of the research

The research is limited as follows:

1. Spatial limits: This concerns the city of N'Djamena, the capital, which is home to several local radio stations, including DJA-FM radio.
2. Temporal limits: Between the five years 2016-2020.

Search terms

Impact: This refers to information relayed by the press or its successors, and impact is the mark left by something or resulting from an action. Another definition: impact in the universal dictionary. Arabic-Arabic dictionary.

impact: the remainder of something, and in the plural آثار وأثر, and we say خرجت في أثره and خرجت في إثره ³, meaning after it.

Strategy: This is a comprehensive, long-term plan aimed at achieving specific objectives, based on a set of decisions and methods to direct efforts and resources.

It is used in various fields such as business, politics, and warfare, and includes analyzing the current situation, determining strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats, and analyzing how to effectively achieve the objective.

Media : This involves transmitting information, news, and knowledge to the public through various means, such as print media, radio, television, and the internet, in diverse forms ranging from traditional to digital across different fields.

² Al- Zarad and Faysal: Alcohol and Drug Addiction, Dar Al- Ilm , printing, publishing and distribution, Lebanon, 2009.

³ Al- Athar : Definition and meaning of Al- Athar in the Al- Ma'ani Al- Jami ' dictionary, an Arabic-Arabic dictionary. Al- Ma'ani <https://www.almaany.com>, 05/12/2025.

Radio : This is the most widespread and popular means of communication, reaching a general audience of all levels. It can reach this audience by bypassing barriers of illiteracy and geographical obstacles, as well as political restrictions that prevent some other media from reaching their communities, and it does not require total commitment.

Local : Radio stations present within the local territory of a given country, whose programs are established locally, that is, within a limited scope, unlike regional and international stations, and which are also dedicated to their region and local affairs.

Fighting against : Confronting an abnormal phenomenon, event, or situation within the society in which we live today.

Drugs : These are substances that numb the body and senses and plunge the individual into a kind of torpor. Drugs are among the most destructive scourges of modern times, due to their inherent danger, except in emergency situations ⁴.

Search results

Through the study, the researcher arrived at several results as follows:

1. This study clearly demonstrates that local radio stations are an appropriate tool for raising awareness and that their messages resonate deeply within society. 2. The study showed that the work of local radio stations has led to a significant increase in awareness among the Chadian people regarding the dangers of drugs, particularly among young people. 3. Despite some challenges faced by local radio stations, they successfully disseminated their awareness messages and alerts, proving to be an easy and accessible tool for all members of society. 4. The majority of Chadian society is aware of what drugs are, which has enabled local radio stations to highlight the negative aspects of this phenomenon and provide health advice to those who are involved in drug use. 5. DJA-FM radio has developed in order to create awareness programs for large segments of society and to broaden its perspectives, which has allowed it to gain a large number of listeners across the country.

Search recommendations

After summarizing the findings of this scientific study, the researcher recommends the following:

1- Although local radio stations have raised awareness among the Chadian people about the dangers of drugs, they need to adjust their approach and redouble their efforts to reach a larger segment of society. 2- The researcher recommends that the government support local radio stations in their activities, which primarily aim to dispel certain misconceptions within society, and provide them with logistical and technical support so that they can operate professionally and in accordance with local needs.

3- Local radio stations need to improve certain aspects of their work in terms of various facilities within the radio station, and provide written documents and archives that some intellectuals can consult.

4- Modify certain schedules of awareness programs that have educational importance for the targeted citizen so that a wide audience can follow them.

Chapter One: Origin and Evolution of Radio Programs:

Section One: The Role of Radio Types, Their Importance and Characteristics: The Stages of Radio Transmission:

Radio broadcasting begins in the studio with the microphone and ends when the listener tunes into the radio receiver. The stages of radio transmission can be summarized as follows:

First : In the radio studio : Broadcasting begins inside the studio, where the microphone converts sound energy into electrical energy, which is then transmitted to the studio control room.

Second : In the studio control room : In this room, the electrical energy representing the sound coming from the studio is amplified using an amplifier. The sound, now electrical current, is then routed to the main control room in the radio station building. It is worth noting that the studio control room broadcasts the recorded tapes and discs containing all the programs listed on the radio station's daily schedule. The tape and disc recordings pass through the amplifier in the studio control room before being sent to the main control room. It is clear that radio plays an important, indispensable role in all programs, and particularly in entertainment programs, even if this is at the expense of programs with an informative purpose, and which have a considerable impact on the orientation of public opinion, like other mass media ⁵.

Third : In the main control room : In this room, the electrical audio signals from all radio services are collected, as they converge here. These are the sounds that represent the content of each radio service; that is, the electrical current that originally produced the sound arrives in the main control room. The function of this room is to send the electrical audio signals from the various radio services to the transmitting station, and this is done via wireless links connecting the radio building to the various transmitting stations, which are distributed around the world.

Fourth : At the transmitting station : The generator or oscillator located at the transmitter station produces electrical pulses or beats of regular frequency known as carrier waves.

The carrier wave is a wave with a regular frequency capable of carrying sound and propagating over long distances. Propagation depends on the type of wave used for radio broadcasting. For example, medium waves can propagate longer distances than long waves, and short waves can propagate farther than medium waves. The wavelength and frequency vary from station to station, which can cause interference between some stations. Radio waves and frequencies are allocated to different countries by the International Telecommunication Union. With the availability of satellite communication technology, many channels can now be used for radio broadcasting via what is called satellite radio. **Fifth : the reception phase via the radio receiver** : the radio antenna picks up radio waves emitted and broadcast into space. These waves come from national and international stations. Generally, the radio antenna only allows one wave to pass through at a time during reception. This is done using an indicator that controls the choice of wavelengths and allows the selection of the most suitable radio waves and frequencies. This means that the radio's dial controls the modulation of the wavelength via the capacitor also present in the radio. Once the desired wave is selected for listening, the radio then

⁴ Mohamed Miner Hajjaj : The Media Dictionary, Dar Al- Fajr for publishing and distribution, 1st edition, 2004.

⁵ Maguy Helwani : Introduction to radio and television art, publication and distribution, Alame Al- Kutub Printing House , Cairo, 2000.

covers a limited geographical area (local, national, and regional radio stations), but it can also broadcast beyond national borders to distribute its programs (international radio). This means that the radio broadcasts a range of media, educational, and entertainment programs, sending them simultaneously to the listening device ⁶.

Sixth step : the detection process : this operation takes place inside the radio and is the reverse of the modulation performed at the transmitting station.

In this process, the sound of the program broadcast by the radio station is separated from the modulated wave; that is, the audio signal is isolated from the carrier wave. The electrical currents representing sound are sent to the amplifier where they are amplified, and then transmitted to the radio's speaker.

Types of Radio, Their Importance, and Characteristics:

Radio encompasses several types, as follows: 1 - **Local Radio** : This type of radio offers a local service and serves a local community. Its programming is aimed at a specific and limited community living within a small and economically, socially, and culturally homogeneous area, creating a cohesive environment. The

Concept of Local Radio : Local radio is a branch of local media that emerges from a specific and limited environment and targets well-defined groups, thus becoming closely linked to them. It is connected to local culture and the actual conditions of the environment, reflecting the cultural and regional heritage of that environment. It fully embraces the prevailing ideas within that environment, taking into account the dominant ideas of the target audience. Therefore, local radio possesses characteristics that distinguish it from other types of radio.

2- **International Radio** : There are several definitions of international radio, sometimes called directed radio, which can be summarized as follows: A. International radio is radio that transcends the borders of a single state to reach the people of other countries. B. International radio refers to the transmission of music and sounds over vast areas to be received by one or more groups of people outside the borders of the broadcasting state. C. International radio is radio that directs its diverse programs worldwide, with broadcasts in the languages of the people in the countries targeted by these stations. D. Directed radio refers to the broadcasting of a media message from one country to another in a language that the target audience can understand.

The Origin of Targeted International Radio

International radio only became known and saw its modern concept develop after the discovery of shortwave by radio amateurs whose governments had forbidden them from using long and medium waves for leisure due to saturation with broadcast services. International radio spread following the success of amateurs using shortwave. Russia was among the first countries to recognize the importance of this type of communication and its uses in the political sphere; it used radio to spread the word about the Bolshevik Revolution and communist ideas to the world. Radio Moscow, broadcasting in English, alarmed the British government, which promptly severed diplomatic relations with Russia in 1927. This was the first time in the history of international media that diplomatic relations between two countries had been broken off because of targeted radio.

Characteristics of the international radio audience

1- An educated audience, having completed secondary and university studies. 2- The majority reside in cities and urban areas. 3- They have broad political interests. 4- They live in a specific geographic area, such as the Arab region, Northern Europe, or Southeast Asia. 5- Their interests extend beyond their local community, and often even beyond the national and nationalist framework. 6- They rarely correspond with the radio station they listen to, unlike with national radio stations in their own country. 7- Opinion leaders constitute one of the main categories of the audience targeted by international radio, and they listen to these stations to use their content in discussions with their peers, colleagues, and friends. 8- Many international radio listeners are hesitant to correspond with these stations, especially in countries that impose strict censorship on their citizens' correspondence. 9- The characteristics of the international radio audience are largely linked to the level of democracy and the atmosphere of freedom reigning in a country. 10- International radio stations encounter many difficulties and obstacles in understanding the trends of their listeners and the characteristics of their audience.

Skills for preparing radio programs:

The program as a concept : this is the budget, the list of courses, or the plan of what you are going to produce.

The program in practical terms : this is all the content, whether audio or video, broadcast via radio or television for a given period and with a specific objective, which is to reach listeners or viewers. Programs are distinguished from one another by the melody of their introduction and conclusion, their broadcast length, and the time they are broadcast to the public.

Types of discussion programs : there is a set of discussion programs, whether radio or television, that share certain characteristics.

Here are the types of these programs:

1. Discussion programs. 2. Live programs. 3. News programs. 4. Competition programs. 5. Cultural programs. 6. Children's programs. 7. Social programs. 8. Sports programs. 9. Economic programs.

Chapter Two: Harm Caused by Drug Use:

Physical and Mental Damage: The researcher describes how doctors and healthcare professionals state that the use of certain types of drugs can cause insanity, impair memory, transmit neurological, infectious, and gastrointestinal diseases, paralyze mental agility and thinking, affect the intestines in the digestive system, cause loss of appetite, lead to malnutrition and lethargy, weaken sexual function, cause stiffening of tissues and arteries, and also cause skin damage and risks to the body, which manifest as follows:

1. Palpitations caused by repeated intravenous and subcutaneous injections. 2. Discoloration of veins in the elbow, forearm, thigh, leg, etc. 3. Fusion and hardening of veins (sometimes over a length of about 20 cm). 4. Yellowing of the mucous membranes (pallor due to anemia, iron deficiency, hemolysis, blood donations in exchange for local food, which also leads to damage to the lymph nodes), which includes:

⁶ Abdulaziz Sharaf : Introduction to the Media, Dar Al- Kitab Al- Masri , Cairo, Egypt.

- a. Swollen lymph nodes in the shoulder.
- b. Disorders of white blood cells and lymphocytes, which can also lead to damage in other parts of the body.
- c. Injuries caused by inflammation at the injection site. d. Inflammation of the arteries resulting in loss of pulse following injection, causing head injuries and violence. e. The drug covers almost anything ingested, inhaled, injected, or sucked through the mouth, including drugs and prohibited substances, beverages, cigarettes, tobacco, and other items .

It also causes damage to the heart, which manifests as follows:

1. Hypertension. 2. Heart valve damage. 3. Right and left atrial insufficiency. It also causes damage to the lungs, which manifests as follows: 1. Pulmonary hypertension. 2. Pneumonia. It also causes damage to the urinary and reproductive systems, which manifests as follows: 1. Kidney: renal failure. 2. Hepatitis. 3. Severe pain from kidney stone attacks. Reproductive system: in men, it causes erectile dysfunction, infertility, and premature ejaculation; in women, it causes a decrease in libido , etc.⁷

Psychological, moral, and social damage

A person addicted to drug use exhibits deplorable traits and adopts shameful habits, including cowardice, lying, and contempt for moral values. Drug use also leads to the commission of crimes such as theft, rape, adultery, highway robbery, and murder. The drug user also loses their moral principles and neglects their duties. It is well known that colonial countries use the promotion of drugs as a formidable weapon to break the strength of their people, corrupt the nation's morals, and extinguish the spirit of struggle and resistance. There is no doubt that the spread of drugs in a country constitutes a factor of weakness that the enemies of Islam strive to maintain and prolong. Among some drugs is qat , which is described as: "a persistent plant that grows in mountainous regions and in several countries such as Yemen, Sudan, Somalia, Ethiopia, and others."

Qat is considered beneficial, curing fever and digestive system ailments. Scientists have noted that qat has a sedative effect on the human nervous system and that excessive consumption can lead to psychological disturbances ⁸. Stimulants

comprise a group of substances that act on the central nervous system. Among the best known is caffeine, found in coffee and tea, the use of which is not considered dangerous and does not lead to addiction, unlike other stimulants such as qat , among others ⁹.

Economic Damage

Drug addiction causes economic disruption, starting with the individual, then affecting the family, and finally society as a whole. Since the individual is an integral part of society, a decrease in their productivity leads to a decrease in society as a whole. If an individual succumbs to drugs and becomes deeply immersed in them, the following consequences result: 1. Drug use in any form exhausts the body, leading to laziness and inertia, thus rendering the individual incapable of fulfilling many obligations and making them passive in most situations. 2. Drug use leads the user to spend exorbitant sums on drugs, representing a significant loss for themselves, their family, and society. They are willing to sacrifice themselves even physically and are unable to manage their household budget; they always prefer to buy drugs at any cost, which is a loss for their family, without realizing that drugs are also harmful to society.

3. Almighty God has forbidden extravagance, making it a forbidden act, and has described extravagant individuals as brothers of the devils. Extravagance consists of spending on falsehood. It is clear from the above that drugs lead to the loss of the five pillars that Islam strives to preserve, and which all divine laws have enunciated: religion, life, intellect, chastity, and material possessions. The drug user quickly loses their faith by voluntarily ceasing to pray, then the other pillars follow, and the structure collapses from its foundations. Thus, it is possible to protect young people by strengthening protective factors and reducing the risk factors surrounding the individual. Raising awareness among all those responsible for education, instruction, and training about the risk factors threatening young people in their society from the dangers associated with the consumption of psychoactive substances directly contributes to reducing the low level of awareness of the dangers of drugs. This also indicates that drugs cause serious physical and mental health damage, and their use can lead to loss of life due to terrible accidents committed by those who use them ¹⁰.

He also informs us that drugs cause serious damage and consequences for mental health, and that their use can lead to loss of life due to horrific accidents committed by users.

They also cause brain damage, preventing the mind from functioning normally, and drug use can drive a person to offer their wife, son, or sister to dealers and traffickers for a dose or injection, even losing their sense of modesty from the very first moments of use ¹¹.

DJA-FM Radio , and the Nature of its Programs. Presentation of DJA-FM Radio

DJA - FM Radio is considered one of the private radio stations operating in the local Chadian media landscape. It is the first independent private radio station founded in N'Djamena by ordinary citizens. The idea to create this prestigious radio station came from a group of patriotic individuals hoping to change certain habits within Chadian society, which had previously suffered from divisions, wars, and conflicts. At their head was Mrs. Zahra Mahamat. Yacoub in May 1998. This woman also worked in the media field both within and outside the country. Radio DJA-FM is located

⁷ Mansour Abdulmajid Sayed Ahmed: Addiction, its causes and preventive and therapeutic manifestations, Ministry of the Interior, Drug Control Research Center, Riyadh, 1406 AH.

⁸ Jafar and Hassan: Drugs and tobacco and their harmful effects, Dar Al- Harf Al- Arabi for printing, publishing and distribution, Lebanon, 2002.

⁹ Atiyat and Abdulrahman Shaaban : Drugs and Dangerous Substances and Responsibility for Combating Them, Naif Arab Academy of Security Sciences, Riyadh.

¹⁰ National Commission for the Fight Against Drugs: Prevention of the Consumption of Drugs and Psychoactive Substances, Between Theory and Practice, Review of the Ministry of the Interior, 2016.

¹¹ Mohamed ben Yahya Al- Najimi : Drugs and their rules in Islamic Sharia, Research and Study Center, Naif Arab University for Security Sciences, 1st edition, 2004.

in the Ambassatna neighborhood, in the third arrondissement, on General Charles de Gaulle Street, near the capital's central market and the grain market. It broadcasts its programs on FM 96.9. The building is rented, and the rent amounts to two million (2,000,000) per year.

The idea and methods of creating the radio station:

The idea for DJA-FM radio arose after its founders noticed a lack of awareness among the Chadian people regarding certain immoral behaviors, as well as a lack of cultural and health awareness within society at the time and even today.

Since then, the radio station has broadcast programs that had been planned in advance, striving to translate and implement the established objectives within the realities of daily life.

Reasons for the creation of DJA-FM radio : Among the reasons that led to the creation of this radio station was the fact that the national radio was a government radio station operating according to a plan established by the state. This meant that it did not have sufficient or complete freedom to broadcast information concerning state policy. Thus, freedoms were limited, and at that time, there was no other radio station capable of making its voice heard by the population besides the Chadian national radio.

It was also noted that there was no space for freedom of expression, nor for those who wished to have their voices heard. DJA-FM radio was created to broadcast the events and news that Chadian society demanded, in order to overcome such obstacles. Therefore, it was a free and independent radio station, capable of fully fulfilling its mission.

Among the other reasons that led to the creation of DJA-FM radio, there is the need for Chadian society to have a radio that expresses its opinion and broadcasts educational, health, entertainment and other programs.

Funding Sources : The radio station receives no external support from any organizations or civil society associations. Its revenue comes primarily from announcements and advertisements, as well as notices such as missing children or death notices. However, some of these types of announcements have disappeared over time, leaving only the most significant ones.

Currently, the radio station relies on the income provided by its director, Ms. Zahra Mahamat . Yacoub, who covers the radio station's expenses as well as those of its staff. Occasionally, the radio station also receives specific grants from the Chadian government and local media outlets—whether audio, visual, or print—as part of initiatives to encourage and stimulate these media institutions.

Stages of Radio DJA-FM's development : The radio station has gone through several stages since its creation. Initially, it used traditional equipment consisting of recording devices that operated with small magnetic tapes, gradually evolving towards the modern digital system used by most local and international radio stations worldwide.

The radio station's beginnings were traditionally somewhat modest, like many international, regional, and local stations, until it experienced development and growth in both performance and evaluation, as well as in the technical equipment acquired.

DJA -FM Radio's objectives : The radio station clearly defined its objectives from its inception in order to follow understandable methods and approaches, and to make its vision clear to its listeners, the citizens of Chad. These objectives include:

1. Working to change certain negative behaviors in the daily lives of some.
2. Fully raising awareness among Chadian citizens regarding education, culture, and other matters.
3. Eliminating and rejecting hatred and sectarianism among the country's inhabitants.
4. Contributing, through its various programs, to the development and advancement of the country and its citizens.
5. Fighting corruption within Chadian society.
6. Changing certain negative practices and traditions in place.
7. To disseminate necessary information and news to the population, both locally and internationally.

Types of programs offered by DJA-FM radio : Regarding program production and recording, this radio station has played a significant and extensive role by offering a variety of programs that have contributed to raising awareness among Chadian citizens and fostering closer ties between Chadian cultures from north to south. The types of programs offered by this radio station include:

1. Educational programs.
2. Social programs.
3. Political programs.
4. Cultural programs.
5. Health programs.
6. General programs.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the researcher can only mention a series of difficulties encountered in his journey and efforts to complete this work and scientific duty. This study has undoubtedly contributed to enriching his knowledge through his engagement with books, manuscripts, and libraries. The choice of this topic—namely, the impact of media strategies on local radio stations to combat drug use, using Radio DJA-FM as a model—was motivated solely by scientific research objectives and the desire to uncover certain truths about this fascinating subject. This study allowed the researcher to acquire diverse scientific and health-related insights. After considerable effort, the researcher was able to identify the appropriate elements for this topic, hoping that they would meet the scientific objectives and benefit those curious and passionate about knowledge.

Research Results

Through this study, the researcher achieved the following results:

6. This study clearly demonstrates that local radio stations are an appropriate tool for raising awareness and that their messages resonate deeply within society.
7. The study showed that the work of local radio stations has led to a significant increase in awareness among the Chadian population regarding the dangers of drugs, particularly among young people.
8. Despite some challenges faced by local radio stations, they successfully conveyed their messages and awareness campaigns, proving to be an easy and accessible tool for all members of society.
9. The majority of Chadian society is aware of what drugs are, thus paving the way for local radio stations to present the negative aspects of this phenomenon and provide health advice to those who are involved.
10. DJA-FM radio has developed its programs with the aim of expanding its awareness programs to broad segments of society and broadening its perspectives, which allows it to gain a large number of listeners across the country.

Research Recommendations

After completing the final image of this scientific study, the researcher recommends the following:

5- Despite the efforts of local radio stations to raise awareness among the Chadian people about the dangers of drugs, they need to revise their approach and increase their efforts to reach a larger segment of society. 6- The researcher recommends that the government support local radio stations in their activities, which primarily aim to dispel certain misconceptions, and provide logistical and technical support so that these stations have a conducive environment to carry out their missions professionally and in accordance with local aspirations.

7- Local radio stations should improve certain aspects of their work, particularly their internal facilities, and provide written documents and archives that scholars could consult.

8- It is necessary to adjust the scheduling of some awareness programs, which are important for educating the target audience, so that a wider public can access them.

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